

THE EFFECT OF BRAND EQUITY ON PURCHASE DECISIONS AT BANJARMASIN ISLAMIC HOSPITAL, INDONESIA SERVICES

Ali Mukaramⁱ,

Marijati Sangen,

Ahmad Rifani

Master of Management,

Lambung Mangkurat University,

Banjarmasin, Indonesia

Abstract:

The tight competition in the hospital services industry requires each of these service providers to fix the services they provide to consumers. The hospital as a service provider must understand the expectations and desires of consumers well so that in the end the hospital will be able to provide services expected by consumers, this will certainly have an impact on the brand of the hospital itself. A brand makes it possible for hospitals to compete in the sale of products or services and shows the proportion of the value of its business strategy, therefore it is strategically very important to develop, filter and improve the brand of a product or service. This study focuses on analyzing the influence of brand equity variables on service purchase decisions, analyzing the influence of brand awareness on service purchase decisions, analyzing the influence of brand associations on service purchase decisions, analyzing the effect of perceived quality on service purchase decisions, and analyzing the effect of brand loyalty towards purchasing service decisions at Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. This research is explanatory using survey research methods. The type of data used in this study is qualitative data and quantitative data. The data sources used in this study are primary data and secondary data, namely the results of interviews, questionnaires and data on the average number of days of care or Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR) of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. The sampling technique uses purposive sampling with multiple regression analysis with a total sample of 100 people. The results of regression coefficient show that all independent variables (Brand Equity, X) consist of Brand Awareness (X1), Brand Association (X2), Quality Perception (X3) and Brand Loyalty (X4) have a positive regression coefficient ie $X1 = 0.691$; $X2 = 0.147$; $X3 = 0.067$; $X4 = 0.081$ this shows that the independent variables are proportional to the dependent variable, namely the Purchase Decision. The degree of relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable can be seen from the coefficient of determination

ⁱ Correspondence: email mkipaunlam@gmail.com

(R Square) where it is known that the value of R Square in this study is 0.964 (96.4%). This shows that the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable (Brand Equity) on the dependent variable (Purchasing decision) is 96.4%. The results of the study show that the three sub-variables of brand equity affect the purchasing decisions of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital services, namely brand awareness, brand association, and brand loyalty. While the perception of quality is considered to have no significant effect.

Keywords: brand equity, purchase decision, service

1. Introduction

Health services have become a profitable industry and attract investors to invest their capital now. The last few years the development of hospital services is growing and developing rapidly, this is characterized by the emergence of several types of hospitals, clinics and other health services, from basic and simple health services to complete and modern health services. The hospital as a service provider must understand the expectations and desires of consumers well so that in the end the hospital will be able to provide services expected by consumers, this will certainly have an impact on the brand of the hospital itself. Business strategies can be formed through brands. A brand makes it possible for hospitals to compete in the sale of products or services and shows the proportion of the value of its business strategy, therefore it is strategically very important to develop, filter and improve the brand of a product or service. Manufacturers or service providers also benefit greatly from the brands they have. At the most minimal level the brand will greatly facilitate the producers or service providers in conducting marketing activities in the form of promotion of products to be sold because of the clarity of the inherent identity. All marketing, production and financial processes can only run optimally if the product has a clear identity. If the brand has been patented, the company will get legal protection from the efforts of other parties who will take advantage illegally, so that financially the company or service provider can benefit for a relatively long term. In the context of the target market, the company brand can build the image it wants and build competitive advantage in the market.

At present the size of the market share of hospital services is both an opportunity and a challenge that must be utilized by management to win the hearts of consumers, therefore hospital service providers must be fully aware that brands must be the identity of a company or product and become selling value added services to consumers. One factor that supports consumer decisions in buying a product is the brand (Kotler & Keller, 2009).

Brands are very important in the digital age and information systems that are increasingly easy now, consumers will be very easy to find information about the brand of a product or brand of hospital services and then compare it with other health care

providers. A strong brand will make a hospital service more trusted and has its own place in the consumer's heart (positioning), and will increase the hospital's prestige in the eyes of consumers. Strong brand equity is a valuable asset for a company or service provider where the stronger brand equity is owned, the greater the attractiveness of inviting consumers to buy products or services provided. According to Rangkuti (2004) brand equity is a consideration of consumers in making purchasing decisions on a product or service. Brand equity is able to shape consumer perceptions of products or services that are believed to have higher quality than other products. According to Arnold (1996) when consumers are increasingly selective about the decision to buy a product or service, the brand equity strategy can provide added value to companies and consumers. Brands that have equity mean positively responded by consumers who can then develop into the basis of the process of consumer purchasing decisions.

Data from the South Kalimantan Provincial Health Office, 38 hospitals operating in South Kalimantan, consisting of 21 state-owned hospitals and 17 private hospitals, are currently one of the most calculated health service centers in South Kalimantan. Especially in the city of Banjarmasin is the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital/Rumah Sakit Islam Banjarmasin (RSIB). Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital has 13 outpatient clinics which are supported by specialist doctors who are reliable and professional in their fields, and have several choices of inpatient care rooms equipped with beautiful gardens. The choice of room type consists of Super VIP, VIP, Class I, Class II, Class III, and Intensive Care Unit (ICU) treatment rooms as well as the Renal Center room and 24-hour laboratory services, Emergency Installation (EDD), Radiology and Ultra Sonography, Pharmacy and other supporting services.

In the midst of intense competition in the provision of health services is a challenge that must be faced by the Islamic Hospital of Banjarmasin, in addition to the government's policy regarding the obligations regarding social health insurance managed by the Social Security Organizing Agency (BPJS), it also makes it easier for people to access services cheap and quality health is also a challenge for the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital in an effort to increase the number of inpatient visits or Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR).

In 2014, the Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR) in Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital amounted to 60.21%, in 2015 it was 55.11% and in 2016 it decreased to 46.48% and in 2017 it declined again to 34.61% (Medical Record RSIB, 2017). BOR data is an indicator of the performance of a hospital. From the BOR data of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital continues to decline from 2014 to 2017, and compared with the standard BOR which is ideal for hospitals of 60-85% (Depkes R. I., 2005), a temporary conclusion can be made that the patient's interest in treatment to the Islamic Hospital Banjarmasin tends to decline, this indicates that the management of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital needs to improve its marketing strategy to increase the BOR as an indicator of the performance of a hospital. One of the efforts that can be carried out by the management of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital is by measuring the strength of the brand. The measurement of a brand can be done to find out the strength of the brand, namely by

measuring the brand equity element which consists of Brand Awareness, Perceived Quality, Brand Association and Brand Loyalty (Brand Loyalty), so that by knowing the strength of the brand, management can make a strategy to develop and capture the market share of hospital health services.

The results of interviews with 10 respondents who were treated at the Islamic Hospital Banjarmasin stated that Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital provided quality services, prioritized patient safety, and nurses performed medical actions correctly. Respondents also stated that Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital served patients well and cared and cared for the needs of customers or patients, respondents also stated that Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital provided standard facilities and also had a reliable laboratory and radiology, besides 6 out of 10 respondents stated that rooms were the size of the building is still narrow, the buildings that are quite old make the rooms look less attractive, the bathrooms and lavatories look less clean, and the difficulty of finding parking spaces for cars. 5 respondents also stated that they were likely to use Islamic Hospital services if there were families who experienced illness and needed hospitalization while the other 5 said they thought they would be treated at the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.

Research of Nugroho (2013), which examined the effect of brand equity on the decision to use and reuse (future use) Muhammadiyah Hospital in Surabaya, stated that there was a significant influence between brand awareness of the use and reuse of Muhammadiyah Hospital in Surabaya. While in the research of Pradipto, et al. (2016), the results obtained simultaneously brand equity has a significant effect on purchasing decisions, while partially brand equity variables show significant results on purchasing decisions, except brand awareness that has no significant and negative effect on decisions purchase.

Alfionita's, et al. (2016) shows the results that brand equity variables have a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Partially, the variable brand awareness, brand association and brand loyalty shows a significant influence on purchasing decisions, while the impression of quality does not have a significant effect. Variables that have dominant influence on purchasing decisions are brand awareness variables. However, the results of Pratiwi's, et al. research (2012) show that together brand awareness variables, brand associations, the impression of quality, brand loyalty, and other ownership assets have a significant influence on purchasing decisions. Partially brand association variables, the impression of quality and brand loyalty shows a significant effect on purchasing decisions. Whereas the brand awareness variable and other ownership assets show insignificant influence. The dominant variable influences consumer purchasing decisions, namely the quality impression variable.

Komang Suharyani's (2015) research shows that brand equity has a significant effect on purchasing decisions of Botol Sosro tea products in terms of the dimensions of brand awareness, brand association, brand loyalty and perceived brand quality. But Sudomo (2013) research shows different results, partially, brand awareness and brand loyalty variables have a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, while

brand association variables and perceived quality do not significantly influence purchasing decisions.

2. Methods

2.1 Research Framework

The method in this study is included in survey research. Survey research is generally carried out to take generalizations from in-depth observations. This research is explanatory, namely research that intends to explain the position of the variables studied and the relationship between one variable and another variable (Sugiyono, 2005). The research framework used is based on the following chart flow.

The type of data used in this study is qualitative data and quantitative data. The data sources used in this study are primary data and secondary data. Primary data are data collected from interviews and using questionnaires to health care users at Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. The researcher asked the respondents to provide answers to questions in a closed questionnaire. While secondary data in the form of information obtained from data on the average number of days of care or Bed Occupancy Rate (BOR) Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. The unit of analysis in this study was users who had purchased inpatient services at the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.

The sampling technique used in this study was purposive sampling. The population in this study were people who were hospitalized at the Islamic Hospital Banjarmasin at the time of this study, which was between April and May with a population of 905 people, while the target sample was part of the population with

characteristics that had been determined. The selected sample must meet the requirements to be suitable as a data source. The conditions are:

1. Respondents are patients or their families who are hospitalized at the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.
2. Aged over 19 years, this is because respondents with this age are considered adults and understand the questions asked and can take a decision (the age limit of children according to WHO criteria is 19 years).

3. Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis in this study is based on the opinion of Aaker (1991) that brand equity can influence consumer confidence in making purchasing decisions on the basis of past experience in the use of close associations with various brand characteristics. Some previous studies also mentioned that brand equity variables (brand awareness, brand association, perceived value, and brand loyalty) proved to influence the decision to buy a product or service.

The hypotheses presented in this study are:

H1: Brand equity consisting of brand awareness, brand association, perceived quality, brand loyalty influences the purchase decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital health services. This hypothesis is based on the opinion of Aaker (1991) which states that brand equity can influence consumer confidence in making purchasing decisions on the basis of past experience in the use of close associations with various brand characteristics.

H2: Brand awareness affects the purchasing decisions of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital health services. This hypothesis is based on the opinion of Durianto, et al. (2001) which states that consumers tend to buy a known brand, they feel safe, avoid various usage risks assuming that the brands that are already known are more reliable.

H3: Brand associations affect the purchasing decisions of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital health services. This hypothesis is based on the opinion of Durianto, et al. (2001) which states that generally brand associations become the basis of consumers in purchasing decisions and loyalty to the brand.

H4: Perception of quality affects the purchasing decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital health services. This hypothesis is based on the opinion of Rangkuti (2004) which states that the perception of the quality of a brand provides an important reason to buy. This affects which brands should be considered and then influences what brands to choose.

H5: Brand loyalty affects the purchasing decisions of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital health services. This hypothesis is based on opinion, Durianto, et al (2001) which states that a customer who is very loyal to a brand will not easily moves his purchase to another brand, whatever happens with the brand.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Validity Test Results and Instrument Reliability

Validity and reliability tests were not tested on all respondents but only in the preliminary sample, which was 30 respondents (Suliyanto, 2006). Based on the results of the questionnaire from the respondents showed that all question instruments are valid because the coefficient value (r) is greater than 0.3. As for the value of measuring reliability based on the results of the analysis, it is also seen that all instruments of the Chronbach Alpha (α) value are greater than 0.6. Based on the results of the analysis that has been done for the value of r (validity coefficient) and the Chronbach Alpha value (α), it can be concluded that all instrument questions are feasible to be used in this study.

4.2 Multicollinearity Test

This classic assumption testing is generally done on variables that have 2 or more explanatory variables. According to Nugroho (2005) a linear regression model can be said to be a good model if the model meets the normality of the data and is free from classical assumptions, namely multicollinearity, autocorrelation, and heterosyndity.

A. Multicollinearity Test

This test was conducted aiming to see whether there was any correlation between independent variables found in the multiple regression model. A good regression model should not have a correlation between the independent variables (Ghozali, 2016). According to Nugroho (2005), testing of multicollinearity also aims to avoid habits in the conclusions process regarding the effect on the partial test of each independent variable on the dependent variable.

Table 1: Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistic	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
Constant	1.113	0,957		1,163	0,248		
X1	0,080	0,079	0,077	1,018	0,311	0,379	2.363
X2	0,070	0,045	0,146	1,546	0,125	0,243	4,121
X3	-0,011	0,056	-0,019	-0,199	0,843	0,227	4,402
X4	0,358	0,047	0,727	7,620	0,000	0,239	4,190

The VIF value of the four independent variables is not more than 10 and the Tolerance value is not less than 0.1, which means there is no correlation between the independent variables whose value is more than 95% so it can be concluded that the linear regression model is free from multicollinearity.

B. Heteroscedasticity Test

This test was conducted aimed at testing the difference in residual variance in a period of observation to another observation period, or a description of the relationship between the values predicted by the Studentized Delete Residual value (Nugroho, 2005). This study uses the Park Test to detect heteroscedasticity, that is by looking at the beta parameter coefficient of the regression equation if the beta parameters are not statistically significant, the empirical model data estimated there are homoscedasticities and vice versa.

Table 2: Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
Constant	0,746	0,540		1.380	0,171
X1	-0,094	0,044	0,319	-2,109	0,381
X2	0,029	0,026	0,212	1,120	0,265
X3	0,068	0,032	0,422	2,158	0,333
X4	-0,051	0,027	-0,365	-1,914	0,059

The results of the analysis show that the parameter coefficients for each independent variable (X1, X2, X3 and X4) are not significant, so it can be concluded that the regression model has no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

C. Normality Test

There are two ways to detect whether the residual variable is normally distributed or not, namely through graph analysis and statistical tests. This study uses the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) non-parametric statistical test. The K-S test is done by making a hypothesis:

H₀ : Residual data is normally distributed

H₁ : Residual data are not normally distributed

According to Nugroho (2005) the guidelines used to accept or reject the hypothesis are:

1. H₀ is accepted if the p-value in the Asimp.Sig (2-tailed) column > level of significant (α).
2. H₀ is rejected if the p-value in the Asimp.Sig (2-tailed) column < level of significant (α)

Table 3: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test Results

	Unstandardized Residual
N	100
Normal Parameter Mean	0.0000000
Std. Deviation	1.22087655
Most Extreme Differences Absolute	0.060

Positive	0.036
Negative	-0.060
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z	0.597
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.868

Based on table 5.42 shows that the value of Asimp. Sig (2-tailed) $0.868 > 0.05$ level of significant (α), so H_0 is accepted and H_1 is rejected so it can be concluded that the residual data is normally distributed.

D. Linearity Test

Linear test is used to determine whether or not the linear model is through the ANOVA test by considering the value of F-Linearity and F Deviation from Linearity. The F-Linearity value shows that the extent to which the dependent variable is predicted lies right in a straight line. If the results are significant ($p < 0.05$), the linear model is suitable for the relationship of the model. Basically, the ideal situation of all cases is located in a straight line so that there is no deviation from the case of linearity. In other words it can be said that the deviation will be equal to zero so linearity really explains the total (combined) between groups in linearity. Whereas F-Deviation from linearity shows that the more significant the value of F is the greater the devian case. And if the value of $p > 0.05$ in the column F-Deviation from Linearity, the data tested can be said to be linearly related. The following table shows the results of linearity testing with alpha (α) 0.05:

Table 4: Linearity Test with ANOVA

Dependent	Independent	Value Linearity F	Sig.	F-Deviation from Linearity	Sig. F-Deviation Linearity	from	Category
Y	X1	115.207	0,000	1.392	0,204		Linier
	X2	110.306	0,000	0,684	0,817		Linier
	X3	112.128	0,000	1.124	0,349		Linier
	X4	337.262	0,000	0,774	0,723		Linier

a. Proof of Hypothesis and Interpretation of Results

1) Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

The results of multiple linear regression analysis in this study can be seen in table 5.

Table 5: The Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis of the
 Effect of Brand Equity on the Decision of Purchasing Services

Dependent Variable	Independent Variable	Regression Coefficient	T	Sig	R partial
Keputusan Pembelian (Y)	Brand Awareness (X1)	691	6.676	.000	0.977
	Brand Association (X2)	147	4.025	.000	0.800
	Quality Perception (X3)	067	1.222	.225	0.964
	Brand Loyalty (X4)	081	2.438	.017	0.890
Constants = -5.295	R Square = 0.964				
F-value = 636.520	Sig. F = 0.000				

All independent variables (Brand Equity, X) consist of Brand Awareness (X1), Brand Association (X2), Quality Perception (X3) and Brand Loyalty (X4) have a positive regression coefficient. This shows that the independent variables are in the same direction as the dependent variable, namely Purchase Decision, meaning that if there are changes between the independent variables both changes up or down then the dependent variable also experiences the same change. So, if the Brand Equity of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital increases, the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Service Services also increases, and vice versa if the Brand Equity of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital decreases, the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Service Services also decreases. The magnitude of the effect of the independent variable (Brand Equity) on the dependent variable (Purchasing decision) is equal to 96.4%.

2) Hypothesis testing

- a) Hypothesis 1: this hypothesis is accepted because F-value is (636.520) > F-table (2.46) with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that Brand Equity affects the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services.
- b) Hypothesis 2: this hypothesis is accepted because t-value for the brand awareness variable (X1) of 6.676 with a significance of 0.000. Thus it is known that this hypothesis is accepted because of t-value (6.676) > t-table (1.660) with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that Brand Awareness influences the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. The regression coefficient of the Brand Awareness variable shows a positive value of 0.691 which means there is a positive or unidirectional relationship between Brand Awareness and the Purchase Decision of Islamic Hospital Services in Banjarmasin. In other words, it can be mentioned if Brand Awareness increases, then the Purchase Decision for Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services also increases, and vice versa. Based on the description, it can be concluded that Brand Awareness has a positive effect on the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services.
- c) Hypothesis 3: this hypothesis is accepted because of t-value (4.025) > t-table (1.660) with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the Brand Association influences the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. Brand Association variable regression coefficient shows a positive value of 0.147, which means there is a positive or unidirectional relationship between the Association of Brands with the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. In other words, it can be mentioned if the Brand Association increases, then the Purchase Decision for Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services also increases, and vice versa. Based on the description it can be concluded that the Brand Association has a positive effect on the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services.
- d) Hypothesis 4: this hypothesis is rejected because t-value (1.222) < t-table (1.660) with a significance level of $0.225 > 0.05$. This means that Quality Perception has

no significant effect on the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services.

- e) Hypothesis 5: this hypothesis is accepted because $t\text{-value} (2.438) > t\text{-table} (1.660)$ with a significance level of $0.017 < 0.05$. This means that Brand Loyalty affects the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. The regression coefficient of the Brand Loyalty variable shows a positive value of 0.081 which means there is a positive or unidirectional relationship between Brand Loyalty and the Purchase Decision of Islamic Hospital Services in Banjarmasin. In other words it can be mentioned if Brand Loyalty increases, then the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services also increases, and vice versa. Based on the description, it can be concluded that Brand Loyalty has a positive effect on Purchase Decision Services of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services.

b. The Implications of The Research Results

Given that there are 3 variables from Brand Equity have a significant effect on Purchasing Services Services of Islamic Hospital Services Banjarmasin, the implications of this study are, to always increase consumer purchases of hospital services, the Brand Equity Variables that have a significant effect consist of Brand Awareness (X1), Brand Association (X2), and Brand Loyalty (X4) need to get serious attention by the management of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital as a service provider. From the analysis of the research discussed earlier, it can be described the implications of the application in an effort to maintain and strengthen Brand Equity through its variables on the Purchasing Services decision of Islamic Hospital Services in Banjarmasin:

1) Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the brand's ability to appear in the minds of consumers when they are thinking of a particular product. Brand awareness is the basic dimension in Brand Equity. A brand has no equity until the consumer is aware of the existence of the brand. Brand awareness which is the first variable of Brand Equity in this study shows a positive influence on Purchasing Decisions. Based on the results of research on this variable, it is necessary for the management of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital to carry out continuous promotions so that brand awareness of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital services is maintained and even increases. This is because brand awareness has an influence on the purchase decisions of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. Promotion can be done in various ways, including through good advertising media such as radio, television, newspapers and billboards or through social media. Advertising in a sharp climate of competition increasingly plays a very large role. Therefore, regularly and planned management of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital must be able to build and enhance its image in the market through continuous advertising, without ignoring various technical factors in communicating products to target markets such as presentation quality, media choice accuracy, message content, and so on. In addition, management can also use slogans or jingles. A slogan or jingle can have a big influence. A jingle can be a tool in creating brand awareness because consumers can

remember jingles or slogans, usually remembering the product. This is done so that consumers remember the brand of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital as a solution to the problem that arises that is when they need health facilities in the form of hospital services.

2) Brand Association

Brand Association is one of the Brand Equity variables that has a positive and significant effect on the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. Based on the results of this study which found a significant influence on the Purchase Decision of Islamic Hospital Services in Banjarmasin, the management of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital must always explore the right Brand Association for superior products from Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital so that promotions are carried out more hit the hearts of consumers. By maintaining and further improving the price policy, and the quality of service, it will further increase consumer associations with the brand of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. Strengthening the meaning of the brand usually depends on the involvement of the Brand Association that occurs. In the Retnawati (2003) study, one form of association that can strengthen brands is product-related associations. Associations relating to this product, Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital must always pay attention to product service innovations provided to consumers, because the failure of innovation will have a broad impact, on the Islamic Hospital brand association itself. Management needs to understand the adjustments to the preferences of consumers and carefully pay attention to competitors' activities.

3) Quality Perception

The Quality Perception Variables in this study indicate Quality Perception has no significant effect on the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. Based on the results of this study which shows that Quality Perception does not affect the Purchasing Decisions of Islamic Hospital management. This can happen because the quality of a hospital has become a standard procedure that must be owned by each hospital, in this study indicators of perceived quality are represented by comfortable treatment rooms, quick responses to complaints, employee friendliness and good, deep laboratory and radiology space. the position of sickness and the need for hospitalization of patients will usually override these factors, however the management of the Islamic Hospital of Banjarmasin must continue to improve the quality of services provided to consumers. Quality must begin with customer needs and end at the customer's perception. In this case consumers who need inpatient services hope that they get good service from doctors, nurses and employees of the Islamic Hospital itself so that it can provide benefits in the form of healing. Management can also improve the quality of service products provided to consumers by conducting continuous research on consumer expectations regarding the quality of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital services. In addition to improving the quality of service products, management must also be able to foster consumer perceptions of quality so that consumer perceptions are in line with the quality of service products sold or provided by the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. To increase Quality Perception by consumers, management can conduct through

demonstration or promotion of service products through advertisements that describe the opinions of people who have used the services of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.

4) Brand Loyalty

Brand Loyalty is one of the Brand Equity variables in this study which also shows that Brand Equity affects the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital Services. Given the importance of customer loyalty to a brand, the management of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital must always maintain and always look for ways to develop Brand Loyalty. Brand Loyalty can be improved and maintained by maintaining excellence and improving factors that are still a weakness of the company. To find out this, management can request consumer opinion about Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital service products through surveys. Management can also use multi-channel to get more loyalty such as using internet sites or call centers. Another way to maintain customer loyalty to the brand of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital is that management must always maintain relationships with customers or consumers. Management can do this through communication with customers through data owned. Management can contact consumers and ask for their response to the Services provided by the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital and provide information back to consumers such as regarding products or service innovations available at Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the results of the analysis carried out, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- a. Variable Brand Equity consisting of Brand Awareness, Brand Association, Brand Loyalty influences the Purchase Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital services.
- b. Variable Brand Equity in the form of Quality Perception does not affect the Purchasing Decision of Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital services.

Based on the results of the research and conclusions that have been stated, the research suggestions can be put forward as follows:

- a. For the management of the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital as a health care provider, it is necessary to make improvements and reform strategies in increasing brand equity. Brand Equity needs to be continuously developed so that the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital is always able to survive as a brand leader in the category of health care providers because based on the results of this study brand equity variables significantly influence the Purchasing Services Decision of Islamic Hospital Services in Banjarmasin.
- b. Given the increasing competition for Hospital services, management needs to be aware of competitor service innovations, especially in aspects of product development. Competitors will continue to strive to strengthen their brands by creating product innovations that are able to compete with the services provided by the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital. Thus, the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital

must be able to continue to innovate so that the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital is always One-step a head compared to its competitors.

- c. The management of the Islamic Hospital should continue to maintain its involvement in community activities such as providing good CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) and can introduce existing services at the Banjarmasin Islamic Hospital.
- d. The results of this study are expected to be used as a reference for the development of further research related to the brand equity of a product.

References

- Aaker, David A. 1991. *Managing Brand Equity Capitalizing on the Value*, The Free Press, New York, Buffa, Elwood.
- Alfionita, C.M., Suharyono, & Yulianto, E. 2016. Pengaruh Ekuitas Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Survei Pada Pembeli Oppo Smartphone di Counter Handphone MATOS). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, Vol. 36 No. 1, pp: 178-185.
- Arnold, David. 1996. *Pedoman Manajemen Merek*. Surabaya: PT. Katindosaho.
- Departemen Kesehatan RI. 2005. *Rencana Strategi Departemen Kesehatan*. Jakarta: Departemen Kesehatan Republik Indonesia.
- Dinas Kesehatan Provinsi Kalimantan Selatan, Profil Kesehatan Dinas Kesehatan Provinsi Kalimantan Selatan Tahun 2016.
- Durianto, Darmadi, Sugiarto & Tony Sitinjak. 2001. *Strategi Menaklukkan Pasar Melalui Riset Ekuitas dan Perilaku Merek*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Ghozali. 2016. *Aplikasi Analisis Multivariate Dengan Program SPSS 20*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia.
- Kotler, P.T. & Keller, K.L. 2009. *Manajemen Pemasaran Jilid 1 Edisi ke 13*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Nugroho, B.A. 2005. *Strategi Jitu Memilih Metode Statistik Penelitian Dengan SPSS*. Yogyakarta: Andi.
- Nugroho, I.S. 2013. Analisis Pengaruh Brand Equity Terhadap Keputusan Masyarakat Dalam Memilih Rumah Sakit Muhammadiyah Surabaya. *Undergraduate Thesis*, Universitas Airlangga.
- Pradipta, D., Hidayat, K., & Sunarti. 2016. Pengaruh Brand Equity Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Survei pada Konsumen Pembeli dan Pengguna Kartu Perdana simPATI Telkomsel diLingkungan Mahasiswa Jurusan Administrasi Bisnis Angkatan 2012 & 2013 Fakultas Ilmu Administrasi Universitas Brawijaya Malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, Vol. 34 No. 1, pp: 138-147.
- Pratiwi, A.C., Suharyono, & Hidayat, K. Pengaruh Ekuitas Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelianparfum Axe (Survei Pada Pria Pengguna Parfum Axe di Kota Malang). *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis (JAB)*, Vol. 4 No. 1.
- Rangkuti, Freddy. 2004. *The Power Brand*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.

- Retnawati, B.B. 2003. Strategi Penguatan Dan Revitalisasi Merek Menuju Pengelolaan Merek Jangka Panjang. *USAHAWAN*, XXXII No. 7.
- Sudomo, St. 2013. Pengaruh Ekuitas Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian (Studi Kasus Konsumen Pepsodent Di Kabupaten Bantul). *JBMA*, Vol. I, No. 2, pp: 33-48.
- Sugiyono. 2005. *Metodologi Penelitian Bisnis*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Suharyani, K., Nuridja, I.M.N., & Haris, I.A. Pengaruh Ekuitas Merek Terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Produk Minuman Teh Botol Sosro Pada Mahasiswa Jurusan Pendidikan Ekonomi UNDIKSHA 2015. *Jurnal Jurusan Pendidikan Ekonomi (JJPE)*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp: 1-13.
- Suliyanto. 2006. *Metode Riset Bisnis*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain copyright to their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Economic and Financial Research shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).